

Synthesis of Isonitrile Complexes of Group-VI Metal Carbonyls and Their Use as Mediator in the [2+2+2]-Cyclization of Alkynes[†]

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A method for selective synthesis of metal carbonyl complexes with certain number of isocyanides has been introduced. The use of these complexes as a mediator in the partially intermolecular [2+2+2]-cyclic cotrimerization of alkynes has also been demonstrated.

Isonitriles have an isoelectronic structure of carbon monoxide, replacing the oxygen atom with the NR unit. Since isocyanides act as better σ -donor and slightly poor π -acceptor than CO when they coordinate to the metal, metal isocyanide complexes are expected to indicate higher reactivity in oxidative addition than the corresponding metal carbonyls. Although metal isocyanide complexes are known to be either obtained by alkylation of cyanometalates or by treatment of metal complexes with free ligand¹, it usually affords the complexed mixture of the products². This difficulty to synthesize is one of the major reasons why organic transformation mediated by metal isocyanide complexes has not been extensively studied yet³. Herein, we have introduced a method for selective synthesis of metal complexes with certain number of isocyanides and showed the use of the complexes as a mediator in the [2+2+2]-cyclic cotrimerization of alkynes.

It is well-known that 'hard' nucleophiles, such as alkyllithiums, attack to the carbon atom of CO on binary Group-VI metal carbonyls **1** directly to afford the Fischer-type carbene complexes **3** (Eq. 1)⁴. On the other hand, known as the Wittig-Staudinger reaction⁵, carbonyl groups are reacted with phosphorimides **4** to give the imines in good yields (Eq. 2). Considering these two reactions, carbon monoxide on the Group-VI metal carbonyls might transform into isocyanide by reacting with **4**. To confirm, a mixture

of alkyl azide (1.2 equiv.), the Group-VI metal hexacarbonyl (1.0 equiv.), and triphenylphosphine (1.2 equiv.) in THF was stirred at 25° for 10 h and the results are shown in Table 1 (Scheme 1)⁶.

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—SYNTHESIS OF MONOISOCYANIDE PENTACARBONYL COMPLEXES OF THE GROUP-VI METAL*

Sl. no.	Alkyl azide (RN ₃)	Yield of 5 (%)		
		M = Cr	Mo	W
1.	<i>n</i> -C ₇ H ₁₅	96	90	97
2.	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	86	89	100
3.	<i>c</i> -C ₆ H ₁₁	76	72	33
4.	<i>tert</i> -C ₄ H ₉	4	8	2
5.	(<i>E</i>)-C ₆ H ₅ CH=CHCH ₂	73	52	84
6.	CH ₂ =CHCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂	99	96	93
7.	HC=CCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂	96	92	98
8.	CH ₃ OOCCH ₂	12	13	78
9.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ SO ₂	(a)	(a)	(a)

*A mixture of 1 mmol of M(CO)₆ (M = Cr, Mo or W), 1.2 mmol of alkyl azide and 1.2 mmol of triphenylphosphine in THF was stirred at 25° for 10 h. (a) *p*-Toluenesulfonyl azide was recovered in >96% yields.

[†] Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev, the outstanding organic chemist in India, on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

In all cases, monoisonitrile complexes were selectively produced under our conditions. The complexes having phosphine, phosphine oxide, or phosphorimide as ligands had not been detected by the analysis of ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra of the crude products. The use of primary and secondary alkyl azides was successful (Sl. nos. 1-3). Steric bulkiness around the carbon attached to the azide group seems to influence to the yields of the products (Sl. nos. 1-4). An alkene and an alkyne in the side-chain were intact during the reaction (Sl. nos. 5-7). However, ester group greatly influenced the yields (Sl. no. 8). While sulfonyl azides did not react with triphenylphosphine at 25° (Sl. no. 9), the desired complex **5** was not produced even at refluxing temperature to give the corresponding sulfonamide. Even when the reaction was carried out in the presence of excess amounts of alkyl azide and triphenylphosphine (5.0 equiv., respectively), **5** was only produced. In contrast, the di- and triisonitrile complexes were also synthesized by thermal decomposition of the monoisonitrile complexes in toluene respectively (Scheme 2). The ir spectra revealed that the diisonitrile complexes had the *cis*-configurations and the triisonitrile ones had the *fac*-ones^{1,7}.

Scheme 2

Since the isonitrile complexes of the Group-VI metal carbonyls are expected to have higher reactivity in oxidative addition than the parent metal carbonyls, we briefly investigated the reaction of the complexes with propargyl bromide in the presence of the diyne **6** and the results are shown in Table 2 (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

Although monoisonitrile complexes reacted with propargyl bromide to produce some intermediates, these did not react with the diyne **6** at all (Sl. nos. 1 and 3). $\text{Mo(CO)}_5(\text{CN-}n\text{-C}_7\text{H}_{15})$ mediated the cocyclization to give **7** in moderate yield. On contrary, the parent metal carbonyls promoted the desired cyclization (Sl. nos. 4 and 5), and molybdenum hexacarbonyl turned out to have the best activity (Sl. no. 7). These results are contrary to our expectations. It might be due to the steric bulkiness around the metal center to

TABLE 2—REACTION OF VARIOUS GROUP-VI METAL COMPLEXES WITH PROPARGYL BROMIDE IN THE PRESENCE OF THE DIYNE **6***

Sl. no.	Metal complex	Equiv.	Yield (%)	
			7	6
1.	$\text{Cr(CO)}_5(\text{CN-}n\text{-C}_7\text{H}_{15})$	1.0	—	83
2.	$\text{Mo(CO)}_5(\text{CN-}n\text{-C}_7\text{H}_{15})$	1.0	13	46
3.	$\text{W(CO)}_5(\text{CN-}n\text{-C}_7\text{H}_{15})$	1.0	—	89
4.	Cr(CO)_6	1.0	62	—
5.	Mo(CO)_6	1.0	67	—
6.	W(CO)_6	1.0	—	79
7.	Mo(CO)_6	0.05	72	—

*A mixture of 1 mmol of **6**, 1.5 mmol of propargyl bromide, and the metal complex in THF was refluxed for 10 h.

prevent the access of the reagents⁸. Although the product, benzyl bromide derivatives, has a possibility to react with the metal complexes, it turned out to remain intact in the present reaction system.

In conclusion, we have demonstrated a new and selective synthetic method of mono-, di-, and triisonitrile complexes of Group-VI metal carbonyls and showed some application to mediate the [2+2+2]-cyclic cotrimerization of alkynes. Further investigation in organic transformation mediated by metal isonitrile complexes are underway.

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